

ACTION OF HALOGEN ACIDS ON ALCOHOLS IN PRESENCE OF BENZENE.

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The reaction of hydrogen chloride with ethyl, *n*-propyl, *n*-butyl and *iso*amyl alcohols has been studied both in presence and absence of benzene. The rate of reaction in absence of benzene follows the order :

The rate, however, increases when benzene is present and this increase is explained by solubility considerations.

Experiments on esterification of organic acids in *iso*amyl alcohol with hydrogen chloride as a catalyst showed that if an inert solvent like benzene were added to the reaction mixture, the rate of esterification increased to many times its original value (Bhide and Watson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2102). By choosing an organic acid like picric acid as a catalyst it was shown that the velocity diminished considerably in presence of benzene (Bhide, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 575). On the basis of these experiments it was suggested that in presence of benzene the change in the rate of reaction is closely connected with solubility of the catalyst in benzene as *iso*amyl alcohol. Thus hydrogen chloride is sparingly soluble in benzene but very soluble in *iso*amyl alcohol. On addition of benzene the hydrogen chloride associates with the alcohol, so that the concentration of the catalyst with respect to the alcohol increases as the concentration of benzene increases, and hence the rate of esterification increases. In the case of picric acid, the acid is more soluble in benzene than in *iso*amyl alcohol so that the catalyst is associated with benzene and the concentration of the catalyst with respect to the alcohol falls as more benzene is added and therefore the velocity of esterification diminishes as the concentration of benzene increases.

As a continuation of the above work the rate of reaction of hydrogen chloride with primary aliphatic alcohols is studied in presence of benzene.

EXPERIMENTAL.

All the alcohols were dried and purified by known methods. Ethyl alcohol was dried over metallic calcium and the rest of the alcohols were dried by keeping them over anhydrous copper sulphate for several weeks.

Benzene was dried over sodium and distilled over phosphorus pentoxide. The densities and boiling points of the substances are given in the following table.

TABLE I.

Atmospheric pressure = 710 mm.

Substance.	Density.	B.P.
Ethyl alcohol	0.7803	76.5-77°
<i>n</i> -Propyl	0.7958	95.5-96°
<i>n</i> -Butyl	0.8008	116-116.5°
<i>iso</i> Amyl	0.8033	131-132°
Benzene	0.8674	78-78.5°

Hydrogen chloride was prepared by the action of concentrated sulphuric acid on pure ammonium chloride and dried over phosphorus pentoxide. The reaction was carried out in pyrex bottles with tight-fitting stoppers at 70° in an electrically controlled thermostat. The vapour pressure of hydrogen chloride in the solution studied is not very high and therefore escape of hydrogen chloride is not possible.

The water formed in the reaction retards the process. Following Hinshelwood (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 599), therefore, initial rates of reaction were calculated by drawing tangents to the curves of percentage change and time. The values of the initial rate, r , expressed as percentage change per minute at 70° for ethyl, *n*-propyl, *n*-butyl and *iso*amyl alcohols are given below. The concentration C of hydrogen chloride is expressed as moles per litre of solution.

TABLE II.

EtOH + HCl.						EtOH + HCl in benzene.				
C	0.1979	0.420	0.6099	0.690	1.013	Benzene (%)	20	40	60	80
$r \times 10^{-4}$	36.67	59.99	67.50	70.0	77.50	C (actual)	0.2002	0.2002	0.1711	0.2084
						C' (effective)	0.2503	0.3337	0.4278	1.042
						$r \times 10^{-4}$	46.57	58.22	66.94	89.19

TABLE III.

<i>n</i> -PrOH + HCl.					<i>n</i> -PrOH + HCl in benzene.				
<i>C</i>	0.2349	0.5597	0.7754	1.285	Benzene (%)	20	40	60	80
<i>r</i> × 10 ⁻⁴	42.97	54.92	62.10	71.63	<i>C</i> (actual)	0.1851	0.1969	0.2014	0.1957
					<i>C</i> ' (effective)	0.2314	0.3281	0.5035	0.9785
					<i>r</i> × 10 ⁻⁴	45.17	55.60	65.19	77.61

TABLE IV.

<i>n</i> -BuOH + HCl.					<i>n</i> -BuOH + HCl in benzene.					
<i>C</i>	0.2966	0.4679	0.7252	0.8847	1.043	Benzene (%)	20	40	60	80
<i>r</i> × 10 ⁻⁴	36.06	47.75	56.26	60.81	64.61	<i>C</i> (actual)	0.2063	0.2005	0.2024	0.1991
						<i>C</i> ' (effective)	0.2588	0.3341	0.5060	0.9955
						<i>r</i> × 10 ⁻⁴	42.02	49.66	59.21	66.85

TABLE V.

<i>iso</i> -AmOH + HCl.					<i>iso</i> AmOH + HCl in benzene.					
<i>C</i>	0.2182	0.4135	0.5007	0.6756	0.9616	Benzene (%)	20	40	60	80
<i>r</i> × 10 ⁻⁴	15.46	22.10	23.53	26.50	28.71	<i>C</i> (actual)	0.2176	0.2475	0.2326	0.2263
						<i>C</i> ' (effective)	0.2720	0.4125	0.5815	1.132
						<i>r</i> × 10 ⁻⁴	17.67	26.51	32.27	37.42

DISCUSSION.

The experimental results are represented in Fig. 1. It will be observed that nature of the curve is the same as that obtained by Hinshelwood (*loc. cit.*) for the reaction of methyl alcohol with hydrogen chloride. The curves also show that the rate of reaction of hydrogen chloride with the alcohols studied follows the following order :

This is quite according to expectations. The effect of introducing a carbon atom in ethyl alcohol reduces the reactivity of the hydroxyl group,

and the reactivity goes on decreasing with the increase in the number of carbon atoms in the alcohol. This behaviour is also observed in many

FIG. 1.

other reactions where the reacting polar group is at the end of a carbon chain. For example the rate of esterification of aliphatic acids follows the order :

This reduction in reactivity usually diminishes with increasing carbon chain and when four carbon atoms are added the reactivity is not affected at all by further increase in the carbon chain.

The effect of adding benzene to the alcohols is seen from the curves given in Figs. 2 and 3. The observed initial rates in presence of benzene increase with the increase in the concentration of benzene. This increase

FIG. 2.

in the rates can be accounted for by assuming that as the benzene concentration increases and the solubility of hydrogen chloride in the alcohols is much greater than in benzene, the hydrogen chloride associates with the alcohol molecules. Thereby the concentration of hydrogen chloride with respect to alcohol molecules is increased. This increased concentration (C' , effective concentration) can be calculated from the following equation :

$$\text{Effective concentration} = \frac{\text{actual conc.} \times 100}{100 - \text{benzene\%}}$$

The rates of reaction expected from this effective concentration of hydrogen chloride are shown by dotted lines. It will be observed that these curves lie close to the curves showing the observed rates of alcohol and acid. The effect of addition of benzene is, therefore, to increase the effective

FIG. 3.

concentration of hydrogen chloride with respect to the alcohols and thus to accelerate the rate of the reaction. This is quite similar to the effect of benzene on the velocity of esterification of organic acids (*cf.* Bhide, and Watson, *loc. cit.*).